

A Quality Control Study of Generic & Branded Domperidone Hydrochloride Tablet

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ABSTRACT

The present study compares generic Domperidone Hydrochloride tablets against their branded counterparts. Physical and chemical parameters were carried out, such as external characteristics, weight variability, hardness, and friability. Chemical parameters tested included assay for active pharmaceutical ingredient and uniformity of dosage unit. The in vitro dissolution test, which simulates what happens after a tablet is swallowed, was conducted to determine how the drug release from each formulation in the body. All the tablets passed the official quality control tests. However, slight differences were detected between the generic and branded tablets regarding the time of dissolution and the mechanical resistance of the tablets. Although generic and branded tablets are considered equivalent, these small differences mean they do not behave identically. This gives reason for the continuous assessment of the quality of Domperidone Hydrochloride tablets so that patients will always receive safe, effective, and reliable medicine.

Keywords: Domperidone Hydrochloride, generic tablets, branded tablets, quality control, dissolution, assay, pharmacopeial standards

INTRODUCTION

Medicines are not only a science; it is also an art. It does not consist of compounding pills and plasters; it deals with the very processes of life, which must be understood before they may be guided. Oral solid dosage forms have been used widely for decades mainly due to their convenience of administration and their suitability for Drug delivery for systemic effects. Tablets has different shapes, sizes, as well as weight depending on medicinal substances and the intended mode of administration. Tablet is the most widely used because of its stability and patient acceptability. With the growth in pharmaceutical industries, number of pharmaceutical products are increasing in market so to maintain its quality is the most primary concern for manufacturers. The same Generic drug can be manufactured by different pharmaceutical companies, which may look like or different than original and sold under different brand name and different cost. Generally, Generic as well as Branded product contains the same type and quantity of the active

ingredient. So, a Generic drug should be identical or bioequivalent to Branded drug with respect to dosage form, safety, strength, route of administration, quality, performance characteristics and intended use. But substandard drugs are also finding place in the market due to ignorance, neglectance and personal profit of pharmaceutical companies and these differ from original product in many aspects like concentration, quality etc. So, to ensure safety and reliability of any pharmaceutical dosage form in terms of quality, pharmaceutical companies should maintain the pharmacopoeia standards (I.P) as prescribed by pharmaceutical regulatory authorities during manufacturing of the drugs.

The proposed study has had performed to provide guideline for the health care professionalizes that can be used to select Domperidone Hydrochloride tablet for patients. The physical parameter i.e., weight variation, length, and diameter, thickness, hardness, friability, disintegration, as well as dissolution were considered during the present study. Different

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physiochemical parameters like variation in weight, length, hardness, thickness, friability, and percent release was calculated. Statistical analysis of dissolution results was performed using repeated measure by UV spectroscopy. So, the quality of the Branded drug commercially available should be ensured in order to assess their quality control which helps in the selection of brand of the drug.

GENERAL CONCEPT

Drug is the single active chemical entity present in a medicine that is used for diagnosis, prevention, treatment & care of a disease. The WHO (1966) has given a more comprehensive definition- "Drug is any substance or product that is used or intended to be used to modify or explore physiological states for benefit of the recipient". The term "drug" is being also used to mean addictive / abused / illicit substances. However, this restricted and degradation of time-honored term, and drug should refer to a substance that has some health promoting / therapeutic / diagnostic application. Nevertheless term 'medicine' is being employed to designate such a substance in place of term 'drug'. A Drug is only active pharmaceutical ingredients (API). Drug has no appropriate dose form and dose. Source of drug are plant, animals, microorganism, minerals, synthetic source, semisynthetic source, recombinant DNA technology. Medicine is a chemical substance which cure the disease, is safe to use has negligible toxicity and does not cause addiction. Medicine is marketed as different dosage form depending on their stability, physiochemical property, aesthetic value and market demand.

GENERIC AND BRANDED DRUG

Generic drugs are those that have exactly the same dosage, intended use, effects, side effects, route of administration, risks, safety, and strength as the original drug. In other words, their pharmacological effects are exactly the same as those of their brand-name counterparts.

Whereas, Brand name of drug refers to the name giving by the producing company, Generic drug refers to a drug produced after the active ingredients of the brand name drug.

A brand name, which is given by the pharmaceutical company that markets the drug. A generic name, that is the drug's 'active ingredient' that makes it work. Generic medicines cost less than brand-name medicines because the manufacturers have not spent money on research and development of the medicine, or buying the rights to sell it.

TABLET

Tablet is a pharmaceutical dosage form. Tablets are solid dosage form each containing a unit dose of one or more active ingredients. They are intended for oral administration. Some tablets are swallowed whole or after being chewed, some are dissolved or dispersed in water before administration and some retain in mouth where active ingredient is liberated. According to the Indian Pharmacopoeia Pharmaceutical tablets are solid, these are flat or biconvex dishes, unit lozenge form, prepared by compressing a medicine or a admixture of medicines, with or without diluents. They vary in different shape and size and weight, depending on number of medicinal substances and the intended mode of administration. Tablets are prepared by compression of equal volume of powder and granules by applying high pressure with help of punches and dies. The excipients include diluents, binders or granulating agents, glidants (flow aids) and lubricants to ensure efficient tableting; disintegrates to promote tablet break-up in the digestive tract, sweeteners or flavoring agents to enhance taste, and pigments to make the tablets visually attractive. A polymer coating is often applied to make the tablet smoother and easier to swallow, to control the release rate of the active ingredient, to more resistant to the environment or to enhance the tablet's appearance.

Fig. 1: Structure of Tablets

TABLET EXCIPIENTS

DILUENTS

Diluents (or fillers) are incorporated in tablet formulations to increase bulk when the active drug quantity is too small to produce a compressible mass. They help improve tablet size, handling, and compression properties.

Examples: Lactose, Mannitol, Sorbitol, Sucrose, Microcrystalline Cellulose (MCC).

BINDERS AND ADHESIVES

Binders are substances added either in dry form or as solutions to impart cohesiveness to powders, enabling granule formation and ensuring that tablets remain intact after compression. They help achieve the desired mechanical strength of granules and tablets.

Examples: (HPMC, HPC), Gelatin (10–20% solution), Glucose syrup (approximately 50% solution).

DISINTEGRANTS

Disintegrants facilitate the breakup of tablets into smaller fragments when they come in contact with gastrointestinal fluids, promoting faster dissolution and improved drug absorption.

Examples: Starch (commonly used at 5–20% of tablet weight), Super disintegrants such as Sodium Starch Glycolate (Primojel), Croscarmellose Sodium (Explotab) used at 1–8%.

LUBRICANTS AND GLIDANTS

Lubricants prevent adhesion of tablet mass to punches and dies, reduce friction during compression, and improve ejection of tablets from the die cavity.

Glidants enhance powder flow by reducing inter-particle friction, ensuring uniform filling of die cavities.

Examples:

Lubricants: Magnesium Stearate, Stearic Acid, Talc, Polyethylene Glycols (PEGs).

Glidants: Corn Starch (used typically at 5–10%).

COLOURING AGENTS

Colorants are added to tablets to improve product appearance, aid in identification, and mask the color of ingredients that may be visually-unappealing.

Examples: Sunset Yellow, Tartrazine, Brilliant Blue, Indigo Carmine.

FLAVOURING AGENTS

Flavoring substances are particularly important in chewable and orally disintegrating tablets to improve palatability. Oils or flavors are often incorporated in dry formats such as spray-dried beads to prevent stability issues.

SWEETENING AGENTS

Sweeteners are included to mask the bitter or unpleasant taste of certain drugs, and improving patient-acceptability.

Examples: Aspartame, Mannitol, Lactose.

DOMPERIDONE HYDROCHLORIDE TABLET

DOMPERIDONE OVERVIEW

Domperidone is a medication primarily used to manage nausea, vomiting, and certain gastrointestinal disorders such as gastroparesis (delayed stomach emptying). It works as a dopamine receptor antagonist, which can also lead to an increase in prolactin levels in the body.

Fig.2: Motilium 10 mg Tablet

SIDE EFFECTS

Common side effects of domperidone include:

1. Headache
2. Dry mouth
3. Abdominal cramps
4. Diarrhea
5. Elevated prolactin levels
6. Due to increased prolactin, patients may experience: Breast changes and milk production.
7. Menstrual irregularities
8. Hypogonadism.

Domperidone may rarely lead to QT interval prolongation and serious cardiac events, including sudden cardiac death. These risks are generally associated with high doses. Although domperidone primarily targets peripheral dopamine D2 and D3 receptors, it can still increase prolactin since the pituitary gland is outside the blood–brain barrier.

USES

Domperidone is commonly prescribed for:

1. Dyspepsia (indigestion)
2. Heartburn and epigastric discomfort
3. Nausea and vomiting
4. Stomach pain in palliative care
5. Occasionally, to increase milk supply in breastfeeding individuals.

METABOLISM

Domperidone is extensively metabolized in the liver and intestines after oral administration, primarily through hydroxylation and N-dealkylation. The major enzyme involved is CYP3A4/5, with minor contributions from CYP1A2, CYP2D6, and CYP2C8. CYP2D6, and CYP2C8.

MECHANISM OF ACTION

Domperidone functions as a gastroprokinetic agent. By blocking peripheral dopamine receptors in the gastrointestinal tract, it:

1. Stimulates gastric emptying
2. Enhances esophageal and gastric peristalsis

3. Reduces small bowel transit time.

DRUG PROFILE

Fig.3: Domperidone Hydrochloride(Chemical Structure)

IUPAC Name: 5-Chloro-1-(1-[3-(2-oxo-2,3-dihydro-1H-benzo[d]imidazole-1-yl)propyl]piperidin-4-yl)-1H-benzo[d]imidazole-2(3H)-one

Synonyms: Domperidona, Domperidonum

Molecular Formula: C₂₂H₂₄ClN₅O₂

Molecular Weight: 425.91 g/mol

Density: 1.3±0.1g/cm³

pH: It is highly soluble at pH 1, while its solubility significantly decreases at pH 6.8

pKa: 7.90

Physical State: Solid at 20°C, Orally disintegrating tablets, suspension & rectal administration in the form of suppositories

Colour: White to slightly beige coloured

Odour: Odourless

Melting Point: 233-236°C

Water Solubility: Low water solubility of Domperidone leads to a low dissolution rate and Variable bioavailability

Stability: More than 90% of original concentration of domperidone remained after 91 days with 95% confidence

Surface Area: 67.92Å²

Route of Administration: Oral

Metabolism: Metabolized in liver & intestine

Duration of Action: 30 to 60 minutes

Bioavailability: 15%

Clearance Route: Through CYP3A4 .

Biological Half Life: 7-9 hr

Table 1.: Generic (Prescription Products) Domperidone Hcl Tablet

Name	Dosage	Strength	Route	Labeler	Date of Marketing
Apo-domperidone-Tab 10 mg	Tablet	10 mg	Oral	Apotex Corporation	1997-09-17
Domperidone-10	Tablet	10 mg	Oral	Pro Doc Limitee	1998-07-13
Dom-domperidone	Tablet	10 mg	Oral	Dominion Pharmacel	1998-09-17
Ftp-domperidone maleate	Tablet	10 mg	Oral	Gmd Distribution Inc.	1998-10-09
Ava-domperidone	Tablet	10 mg	Oral	Avanstra Inc.	2011-09-15
Bio-domperidone	Tablet	10 mg	Oral	Biomed Pharma	2016-04-26

Table 2.: marketed brands of domperidone hcl tablet

NAME	DOSAGE	STRENGTH	ROUTE	LABELLER	DATE OF MARKETING
Motilium Tab 10 mg	Tablet	10 mg	Oral	Janssen Pharmaceuticals	1990-12-13
Motilidone	Tablet	10 mg	Oral	Technilab Pharma Inc.	1997-09-17
Prz-domperidone	Tablet	10 mg	Oral	Pharmaris Cnada Inc.	2018-04-02

QUALITY CONTROL TESTS FOR TABLET

Quality Control Tests of Tablets : Quality control testing of tablets involves the systematic assessment of their physical, chemical, mechanical, biological, and microbiological characteristics. These evaluations are performed in accordance with in-house (non-pharmacopeial) specifications, established pharmacopeial standards such as the Indian Pharmacopoeia (IP), British Pharmacopoeia (BP), United States Pharmacopoeia (USP), and regulatory guidelines including those of the International Council for Harmonization (ICH).

To develop tablets that meet optimal performance requirements and to ensure consistent manufacturing quality, it is essential to evaluate their physical attributes, chemical composition, & bioavailability characteristics. These assessments help confirm that the tablets comply with safety, efficacy, and quality benchmarks throughout production.

Quality control tests used for tablet evaluation are broadly categorized into three major groups:

Non-Official Tests of Tablet: These tests are not restricted or specified in any pharmacopoeia.

1. Thickness and Diameter test
2. Hardness test
3. Friability test .

Official Tests of Tablet: These quality control parameters are outlined either in the individual product monograph or in the general monographs of recognized pharmacopoeias. The essential pharmacopeial tests include:

1. Weight Variation Test
2. Disintegration Test
3. Dissolution Test.

To ensure consistent product quality, these evaluations must be conducted during manufacturing

as part of in-process quality control (IPQC) and subsequently verified after completion of each production batch. This ensures that every batch complies with predetermined quality specifications before release.

WEIGHT VARIATION TEST

Fig.4: Digital Balance

The weight variation test evaluates uniformity of drug content in tablets. It is reliable when tablets are mostly active ingredient ($\approx 90\text{--}95\%$) or when the drug is evenly distributed in the granules/powder. A sample of tablets is individually weighed, and each weight is compared with the average tablet weight. Tablets outside the acceptable pharmacopeial limits indicate non-uniform drug distribution or manufacturing inconsistencies. This ensures consistent dosage and therapeutic efficacy.

Method: Weigh individually 20 tablets selected randomly. Calculate the average weight and comparing individual tablet weights to the average. Tablets meet the IP test if not more than 2 tablets are outside the percentage limits and if no tablets differ by more than 2 times the percentage limit.

Formula Used:

$$\% \text{ weight variation} = \left(\frac{\text{Differences in weight}}{\text{Average weight}} \right) \times 100$$

Acceptable Weight Variation Limit: As per Indian Pharmacopoeia (IP), the acceptable percentage deviation of individual tablet weight from the average depends on the tablet's average weight:

Average weight ≤ 80 mg: Maximum allowable difference = $\pm 10\%$

Average weight > 80 mg and < 250 mg: Maximum allowable difference = $\pm 7.5\%$

Average weight ≥ 250 mg: Maximum allowable difference = $\pm 5\%$

These limits ensure uniform drug content and consistent therapeutic effect in all tablets.

Observation : The observation of above experiment is given in the Table –[1],[2].

HARDNESS TEST

Tablet hardness is the force required to break a tablet by applying pressure across its diameter. It ensures that tablets can withstand handling, packaging, and transport without breaking. Adequate hardness is essential for product stability and also influences disintegration and dissolution, which affect drug release and therapeutic performance.

TABLET HARDNESS DEVICES

Monsanto Hardness Tester: The Monsanto Hardness Tester is one of the earliest devices used to evaluate tablet breaking strength. It consists of a barrel containing a compressible spring positioned between two plungers: a lower plunger in contact with the tablet and an upper plunger that applies force.

Working Principle: The lower plunger is placed on the tablet, and a zero reading is recorded. The upper plunger is gradually forced against the spring by turning a threaded bolt or using a lever, compressing the tablet until it fractures. A pointer on the gauge moves with the spring compression, that indicating the force applied. And The tablet hardness (breaking force) is calculated by subtracting the zero reading from the recorded force.

Fig.5: Monsanto Hardness Tester

Method: One of the earliest testers to evaluate tablet hardness was the Monsanto hardness tester, which was developed approximately fifty years ago. It consists of a barrel containing a compressible spring held between the two plungers. The lower plunger is placed in contact with tablets and zero reading is taken. The upper plunger is then forced against a spring by turning a threaded bolt until the tablet is fractured.

Range: The force with which the tablet is broken is expressed in kg / cm². Oral tablets have a hardness of 4 to 10 kg / cm²; but hypodermic and chewable tablets have a hardness of 3 kg / cm² and sustained release tablets have about 10-20 kg / cm².

Observation: The observation of above experiment is given in the Table –[3],[4]. And the graph is shown in Fig : [12].

FRIABILITY TEST

Friability testing is used to test the durability of tablets during transit (packing, transportation). It is a pharmacopeial test for the evaluation of tablets or quality control tests of tablets. Tablet Friability is the physical condition that describes the tendency of tablets to break into smaller pieces/to detach a percentage of powder or powder loss from the tablet's outer surface under mechanical and physical stress. Since some high hardness tablets tend to be produce capping or lamination after compression thus tablet hardness is not an absolute indicator of strength.

FRIABILITY TEST APPARATUS

Fig.6: Roche Friabilator

Friability tester is known as the Roche Friabilator. Use a drum, with an internal diameter between 283 - 291 mm and a depth between 36 - 40 mm, of transparent synthetic polymer with polished internal surfaces, and subject to minimum static build-up. One side of the drum is removable. The tablets are tumbled at each turn of the drum by a curved projection with an inside radius between 75.5 mm to 85.5 mm that extends from the middle of the drum to the outer wall. The outer diameter of the central ring is between 24.5 mm to 25.5 mm. The drum is attached to the horizontal axis of a device that rotates at 25 ± 1 rpm, which is then operated for 100 revolutions. Drums with dual scooping projections, or an apparatus with more than one drum, for the running of multiple samples at one time, are also permitted.

Friability Formula:

By using following formula, we can calculate friability of tablets:

$$\text{Friability (\%)} = ((W_1 - W_2) / W_1) \times 100$$

W₁ = Initial Weight of Tablets. W₂ = Final Weight of Tablets.

Friability Test Procedure: Verify that the friabilator is calibrated and ensure the drum and surrounding area are clean before beginning the test. Remove surface dust from the tablets thoroughly prior to weighing. For tablets weighing ≤ 650 mg, select tablets with a total weight of approximately 6.5g. For tablets weighing > 650 mg, take 10 tablets as the sample. Record this as the initial weight (W₁). Place the tablets into the drum of the friability tester. The drum allows the tablets to fall a distance of 6 inches (≈ 152 mm) during each rotation. Operate the friabilator for 100 revolutions at 25 rpm. Place the tablets into the drum of the friability tester. The drum allows the tablets to fall a distance of 6 inches (≈ 152 mm) during each rotation. Operate the friabilator for 100 revolutions at 25 rpm. After completion, remove the tablets, dedust them carefully, and determine the final weight (W₂).

Acceptable Friability Limit: A maximum loss of weight (from a single test or from the mean of three test) not Less than 1.0% is acceptable for most tablets. If obviously cracked, chipped or broken tablets are

present in the sample after tumbling, the sample fails the test.

Observation: The observation of above experiment is given in the Table –[5],[6]. And the graph is shown in Fig : [13].

DISINTEGRATION TEST

Disintegration is the initial and essential step that precedes drug dissolution, involving the breakdown of a tablet into smaller granules or its primary powder particles. This process ensures that the drug becomes available for dissolution and subsequent absorption.

All compressed tablets are required to meet pharmacopeial disintegration standards, which are evaluated in vitro using a disintegration test apparatus.

The purpose of the test is to determine whether tablets break apart within the specified time limit when placed in a suitable liquid medium under controlled conditions, such as defined temperature and movement. Disintegration is defined as that state in which no residue of unit under test remains on the screen of the apparatus or, if a residue remains, it consists of fragments of disintegrated parts of tablet component parts such as insoluble coating of tablet. Research has established that one should not automatically expect a correlation between disintegration and dissolution.

DISINTEGRATION APPARATUS

The apparatus consists of a basket–rack assembly, a 1-liter beaker, a thermostatic arrangement for heating the medium, and a mechanical device for raising and lowering the basket at a constant frequency. The basket–rack assembly supports six cylindrical glass tubes, each 77.5 ± 2.5 mm long, 21.5 mm in diameter, and with a wall thickness of approximately 2 mm. The tubes are held vertically by two superimposed transparent plastic plates (90 ± 2 mm diameter, 6.75 ± 1.75 mm thick) perforated with six holes matching the tube diameter. The lower plate's upper surface has a woven stainless-steel wire cloth (plain square weave, 2.0 ± 0.2 mm mesh, wire diameter 0.615 ± 0.045 mm). The upper plate is covered with a stainless-steel disc perforated by six holes ($\sim 24 \pm 2$ mm diameter) that fit

over the tubes to hold them between the plates. The plates are rigidly held 77.5 mm apart using vertical metal rods at the periphery, and a central rod attaches the assembly to the mechanical device. The basket moves up and down smoothly at a constant frequency of 28–32 cycles per minute through a distance of 50–60 mm.

Medium: Distilled water is used as the medium for disintegration test.

Method: Introduce one tablet into each of the six tubes of the basket and immerse in distilled water at room temperature for 5 minutes. Operate the apparatus with the medium maintained at 37 ± 2 °C. Lift the basket from the medium and observe the tablets to ensure they disintegrate completely. Record the disintegration time for all tablets.

Acceptance Criteria Limit: Disintegration time for uncoated tablets: 5 – 30 minutes

Observation: The observation of above experiment is given in Table-[7] And the graph is shown in Fig :[14].

Fig.7: Tablet Disintegration Apparatus

DISSOLUTION STUDY

Dissolution refers to the process by which a solid substance goes into solution. In pharmaceutical evaluation, dissolution testing assesses both the rate and extent of drug release from a dosage form such as tablets, capsules, and semisolid preparations. The dissolution behavior of a drug product is closely

related to its bioavailability and ultimately its therapeutic efficacy.

DISSOLUTION APPARATUS 1

The USP Apparatus I consists of a cylindrical dissolution vessel made of borosilicate glass or another suitable transparent material. The vessel has a hemispherical bottom, a nominal capacity of 900 mL, and an internal diameter between 98–106 mm. It is designed with a flanged rim and a lid containing multiple openings, including one at the center for shaft placement. The apparatus includes the following components:

Motor and Speed Control : A motor equipped with a speed regulator capable of maintaining the specified rotation speed within $\pm 4\%$ of the set value. The stirring assembly consists of a drive shaft attached to a wire basket, which rotates at the defined speed to ensure uniform agitation.

Temperature-Controlled Water Bath: A circulating water bath maintains the dissolution medium at $36.5\text{--}37.5^\circ\text{C}$, ensuring constant temperature throughout testing. The vessel is firmly secured within the bath to minimize mechanical disturbances and prevent vibrations originating from surrounding equipment or the water circulation system.

Fig.8: Basket Type Dissolution Apparatus

Dissolution Medium: The concentration of Domperidone in the dissolution samples was quantified using the drug's previously established calibration curve. The in vitro dissolution study for both generic and branded Domperidone tablets was

carried out using USP Dissolution Apparatus Type I (Basket Method) operated at 50 rpm. The studies were performed in 0.1 N HCl, maintained at $37^\circ\text{C} \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$, which serves as the dissolution medium for simulating acidic gastric conditions performed using USP apparatus type I fitted with a basket (50 rpm) at $37^\circ\text{C} \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$ using 0.1N HCL as dissolution medium .

Method: A volume of 900 mL of 0.1 N HCl was transferred into the dissolution vessel. The medium was warmed to 37.5°C , and the assembly of the apparatus was completed. A single tablet of Domperidone was placed inside a stainless-steel mesh basket, which was then carefully lowered to the prescribed position within the vessel before initiating rotation. The apparatus was operated at 50 rpm for a total run time of 45 minutes. At 15-minute intervals, 5 mL samples were withdrawn from a point midway between the surface of the medium and the top of the rotating basket. Each time a sample was removed, an equal volume of fresh dissolution medium was added to maintain sink conditions and constant volume. The collected samples were appropriately diluted (dilution factor = 10), and the absorbance of each diluted sample was measured using a UV-Visible spectrophotometer at 286 nm (λ_{max}). The corresponding percentage of Domperidone released was calculated. A dissolution profile was then plotted, with time (min) on the X-axis and percentage drug release on the Y-axis, generating the dissolution curve for the formulation. The absorbance values for both generic and branded Domperidone tablets were recorded using a UV-Visible Spectrophotometer (Model 150-02, Shimadzu Corporation, Kyoto, Japan) at 286 nm, with 0.1 N HCl serving as the blank. The λ_{max} was confirmed from the standard calibration plot.

Fig.9: Calibration Curve of Generic Domperidone HCl Tablet (10mg)

Table No.3: Calibration Curve of Generic Domperidone HCl Tablet (10mg)

Concentration (µg/ml)	Absorbance
5	0.159
10	0.359
15	0.586
20	0.769
25	0.958
30	1.161

Fig.10: Calibration Curve of Branded Motilium Tablet (10mg)

Table No.: 4 Calibration Curve of Branded Motilium Tablet (10mg)

Concentration (µg/ml)	Absorbance
5	0.189
10	0.399
15	0.601
20	0.798
25	1.009
30	1.203

Fig.11: Comparison of Dissolution Curve of Generic Domperidone Hydrochloride Tablet (10mg) & Branded Drug Motilium Tablet (10 mg).

ACCEPTANCE CRITERIA LIMIT:

Unless otherwise specified, the requirement is met if the quantities of active substance dissolved from the dosage unit. If the result does not confirm to the requirements at stage S1 given in the table, continue testing with additional dosage units through S2 and S3 unless the results confirm at stage S2. Q* - is the amount of dissolved active ingredients . ** percentage (%) of the labelled content.

Table No. 05: Acceptance Criteria Limit Level

Level	Number Tested	Acceptance Criteria
S ₁	6	Each unit is not less than Q* + 5 per cent.
S ₂	6	Average of 12 units (S1 + S2) is equal to or greater than Q, and no unit is less than Q- 15 per cent**.
S ₃	12	Average of 24 units (S1 + S2 +S3) is equal to or greater than Q, not more than 2 units are less than Q – 15 per cent, and no unit is less than Q – 25 per cent.

Observation: The observation of above experiment is given in the Table –[8],[9].And the graph is given in Fig :[15],[16],[17] .

OBSERVATION & RESULTS:

COMPARISON OF WEIGHT VARIATION FOR GENERIC AND BRANDED DOMPERIDONE TABLET

Table.06: Generic Tablet (Domperidone HCl Tablet) (10 mg)

SI No.	Weight of Individual tablet (mg)	Average Weight	Difference in Weight (mg)	Percentage (%) of weight variation
1	50	$(50 \times 9 + 60 \times 11) \div 20 = 55.5 \text{ mg}$	5.5	9.9
2	60		4.5	8.1
3	60		4.5	8.1
4	50		5.5	9.9
5	50		5.5	9.9
6	60		4.5	8.1
7	60		4.5	8.1
8	60		4.5	8.1
9	60		4.5	8.1
10	60		4.5	8.1
11	50		5.5	9.9
12	50		5.5	9.9
13	60		4.5	8.1
14	60		4.5	8.1
15	50		5.5	9.9
16	50		5.5	9.9
17	60		4.5	8.1
18	60		4.5	8.1
19	50		5.5	9.9
20	50		5.5	9.9
Total - 1110 mg (11.1 gm).				

Table No. 07: Branded Tablet (Motilium Tablet) 10 mg

SI No.	Weight of Individual tablet (mg)	Average Weight	Difference in Weight (mg)	Percentage (%) of weight variation
1	110	$(110 \times 11 + 100 \times 9) \div 20 = 105.5 \text{ mg}$	4.5	4.2
2	110		4.5	4.2
3	110		4.5	4.2
4	110		4.5	4.2
5	110		4.5	4.2
6	100		5.5	5.2
7	110		4.5	4.2
8	110		4.5	4.2
9	100		5.5	5.2
10	100		5.5	5.2
11	110		4.5	4.2
12	110		4.5	4.2
13	100		5.5	5.2
14	100		5.5	5.2
15	100		5.5	5.2
16	100		5.5	5.2

17	100		5.5	5.2
18	110		4.5	4.2
19	100		5.5	5.2
20	110		4.5	4.2
Total – 2110 mg (21.1 gm)				

COMPARISON OF HARDNESS TEST FOR GENERID AND BRANDED DOMPERIDONE TABLET

Table No.07: Generic Tablet (Domperidone HCl Tablet) (10 mg, Uncoated)

SI No.	Individual Hardness of tablets (kg/cm ²)	Average Hardness of tablet
1	5	5.27 kg/cm ²
2	5.5	
3	4.7	
4	5.1	
5	6	

Table No. 08: Branded Tablet (Motilium Tablet) (10 mg, Un-Coated):

SI No.	Individual Hardness of tablets (kg/cm ²)	Average Hardness of tablet
1	7	6.45 kg/cm ²
2	7	
3	6.5	
4	6	
5	5.7	

Fig.12: Comparison Of Hardness Test For Generid And Branded Domperidone Tablet. The graph shows the comparison of Hardness for Generic & Branded Domperidone Tablet.

COMPARISON OF FRIABILITY FOR GENERID AND BRANDED DOMPERIDONE TABLET

Table No.09: Generic Tablet -Domperidone HCl Tablet(10 mg,Un-coated)

SI No.	Average Initial Weight of Tablets(gm)	Average Final Weight of Tablets(gm)	Difference in Weight of Tablets(gm)	Friability Range
1	1.35	1.25	0.1	0.7%

Table No. 10: Branded Tablet- Motilium Tablet(10 mg,Un-coated):

SI No.	Average Initial Weight of Tablets(gm)	Average Final Weight of Tablets(gm)	Difference in Weight of Tablets(gm)	Friability Range
1	1.58	1.57	0.1	0.6%

Fig.13: Comparison Of Friability Test for Generic and Branded Domperidone Tablet. The graph shows the comparison of Friability for Generic & Branded Domperidone Tablet.

COMPARISON OF DISINTEGRATION TIME FOR GENERIC AND BRANDED DOMPERIDONE TABLET

Table No.11: Observation of Disintegration Time for Generic and Branded Tablets

Sr. No	Name of Tablet	Disintegration Time
1.	(Generic) Domperidone HCl Tablet(10 mg, un-coated)	8 minutes
2.	(Branded) Motilium Tablet(10 mg,un-coated)	9 minutes

Fig.14: Comparison Of Disintegration Time For Generic and Branded Domperidone Tablet.

The graph shows the disintegration time of Generic & Branded Domperidone Tablet.

COMPARISON OF DISSOLUTION TIME/ DRUG RELEASE PROFILE FOR GENERIC AND BRANDED DOMPERIDONE TABLET

Table No.12: Drug Release Profile Of Generic Domperidone Tablet (10 Mg)

Sr. No.	Time (minutes)	% of Drug release
1	5	41.72%
2	10	59.26%
3	15	68.15%
4	30	81.98%
5	45	95.47%

Fig.15: Dissolution Curve of Drug(Generic). Here, the graph shows the % of drug(Generic) release with time,So the dissolution pattern is increased with time.

Table No.13: Drug Release Profile of Motilium Tablet (10 mg):

Sr. No.	Time (minutes)	% of Drug release
1	5	41.72%
2	10	59.26%
3	15	68.15%
4	30	81.98%
5	45	95.47%

Fig.16: Dissolution Curve of Branded Drug Motilium Tablet (10 mg).Here, the graph shows

the % of Branded drug release with time, So the dissolution pattern is increased with time.

Fig.17: Comparison of Dissolution Curve of Generic Domperidone Hydrochloride Tablet(10 mg) & Branded Drug Motilium Tablet (10 mg).

CONCLUSION

From the obtained result its been concluded that Domperidone hydrochloride tablet (generic and branded) taken for comparative evaluation of their quality assessment to assure its efficacy and potency gives different results from each other but both generic & branded does not cross the limits given in I.P. The result indicated that although the marketed brand that are already established, manufactured by different pharmaceutical companies can be used interchangeably for anti-sickness treatment. General notion and doubt regarding the quality of the Generic medicines needs to be erased conducting more research studies and publishing them widely. The economic benefits of the use of Generic medicines cannot be denied; and in many countries their use is essential to control healthcare spending. The government and healthcare professionals must take up generic promotional schemes, general awareness programs on quality of generic tablet to increase acceptance of generic tablet among patients.

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